

Synthesis of some novel (1-substituted-5-phenyl-3-trifluoromethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-(substituted benzothiazol-2-yl)-diazene and their antifungal activity

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Abstract : Diazonium salt of substituted 2-aminobenzothiazole (1) has been reacted with 1-phenyl-4,4,4-trifluorobutan-1,3-dione (2) to give compound 3 which on reaction with different hydrazines gives 1-substituted-5-phenyl-3-trifluoromethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl-(substituted-benzothiazol-2-yl)-diazene (4). These compounds have been evaluated for their antifungal activity. The structures of all these compounds have been confirmed by IR, ¹H NMR, Mass spectral, ¹⁹F NMR and elemental analysis. All the synthesized compounds showed significant antifungal activity against selected plant pathogenic fungi.

Keywords : Substituted 2-aminobenzothiazole, substituted hydrazines, 1-phenyl-4,4,4-trifluorobutan-1,3-dione, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Azopyrazoles are successfully used in building up a series of polycyclic nitrogen heterocycles. Some azopyrazoles/pyrazolone rings are used for their diverse application namely for the production of yellow shades on cotton, silk, wool and polyester fibers¹. The pyrazoles are found to be active against leukaemia in mice². Azopyrazoles³ have been screened for their anti-HIV, antibacterial, antitubercular, fungicidal and anticancer activities. Thiazole⁴⁻⁷ moiety is important constituent in the core structure of many of the biologically active compounds. More specifically molecules containing 2-aminobenzothiazole moiety show varied biological activity as antiinflammatory⁸, analgesic⁹, antitubercular¹⁰, antitumor^{11,12}, antibacterial^{13,14} and muscle relaxant activity¹⁵. We envisaged that synthesis of new molecules constituted with both of these heterocycles could give entry to novel bioactive compounds. In continuation to our work¹⁶⁻²¹, we have now synthesized some new derivatives of azopyrazole fused thiazole moiety with enhanced fungicidal activity.

Results and discussion

2-[(Substituted-benzothiazol-2-yl)-hydrazono]-4,4,4-trifluoro-1-phenyl-butan-1,3-dione (3) have been prepared

by diazotization of substituted 2-aminobenzothiazole with 1-phenyl-4,4,4-trifluorobutan-1,3-dione at 0-5 °C with continuous stirring for 2 h. The diazotized form has been reacted with different hydrazines in presence of acetic acid on water bath for 4-5 h to yield 1-substituted-5-phenyl-3-trifluoromethyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl-(substituted-benzothiazol-2-yl)-diazene (4) (Scheme 1).

Compound 3a showed the presence of >NH group in IR spectrum at 3310 cm⁻¹ and in ¹H NMR spectrum showed a singlet at δ 8.4 ppm.

The IR spectrum of the compound 4a showed peak at 1560 (-N=N-), 1660-1720 (>C=C< and >C=N-), 3090 cm⁻¹ (aromatic). ¹⁹F NMR showed peaks at δ -5 to -10 (-CF₃), 30-40 (>C-F) and ¹H NMR showed peak at δ 7.2-8.1 ppm (m, Ar-H).

Fungicidal activity was evaluated against *Alternaria burnsii* and *Macrophomina phaseolina*. All the compounds showed good inhibition of growth due to presence of fluorine atom.

Activity of synthesized compounds :

The antifungal properties of the eight synthesized azopyrazoles were assessed. Separate tests were conducted with each compound with two dosages (100 ppm and 500 ppm). The desired amount of the compound was

Scheme 1

thoroughly mixed in the fungal medium (potato dextrose agar agar) and the test fungus was allowed to grow on the medium for a week. The fungal growth, on the com-

pound mixed medium, was compared with similar fungal growth on medium without test compound. Two plant pathogenic fungi viz. *Alternaria burnsii* (causing cumin

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blight) and *Macrophomina phaseolina* (causing cluster bean stem rot) were selected as test fungi. The present fungal growth inhibition was calculated using following formula.

$$\text{Percent inhibition} = \frac{\text{DT}-\text{DC}}{\text{DC}} \times 100$$

where DT = diameter of fungal colony in compound

mixed medium and DC = diameter of fungal colony on normal medium without test compound.

All the eight compounds gave over eighty percent fungal growth inhibition (Table 2) at 500 ppm dose. The four compounds 4a, 4b, 4c and 4d with four fluorine atoms in their molecules showed excellent antifungal property with 98.23 to 100 percent inhibition in the case of *Alternaria burnsii* and 91.53 to 96.97 percent inhibition

Table 1. Physical and analytical data of the compounds 3a,b and 4a-h

Compd.	R''	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)	Mol. formula	Analysis (%) : Found/(Calcd.)			
					C	H	N	S
3a	-	65	168	C ₁₇ H ₉ F ₄ N ₃ O ₂ S (395.33)	51.51 (51.65)	2.11 (2.29)	10.54 (10.63)	8.02 (8.11)
3b	-	68	170	C ₁₇ H ₉ ClF ₃ N ₃ O ₂ S (411.79)	49.50 (49.58)	2.12 (2.20)	10.05 (10.20)	7.64 (7.79)
4a	-C ₆ H ₅	68	145-148	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ F ₄ N ₅ S (467.44)	58.84 (59.10)	2.72 (2.80)	14.82 (14.98)	6.74 (6.86)
4b	2,4-diNO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	60	199	C ₂₃ H ₁₁ F ₄ N ₇ O ₄ S (557.44)	49.42 (49.56)	1.80 (1.99)	17.40 (17.59)	5.61 (5.75)
4c		67	132	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ F ₄ N ₆ S ₂ (450.44)	47.84 (48.00)	2.06 (2.24)	18.53 (18.66)	14.11 (14.24)
4d		60	160	C ₂₄ H ₁₃ F ₄ N ₅ OS (495.45)	58.06 (58.18)	2.52 (2.64)	14.01 (14.14)	6.31 (6.47)
4e	-C ₆ H ₅	64	90	C ₂₃ H ₁₃ ClF ₃ N ₅ S (483.90)	56.89 (57.09)	2.63 (2.71)	14.33 (14.47)	6.45 (6.63)
4f	2,4-diNO ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	68	162	C ₂₃ H ₁₁ ClF ₃ N ₇ O ₄ S (573.89)	48.08 (48.14)	1.86 (1.93)	16.84 (17.08)	5.41 (5.59)
4g		65	108	C ₁₈ H ₁₀ ClF ₃ N ₆ S ₂ (466.89)	46.20 (46.30)	2.11 (2.16)	17.82 (18.00)	13.60 (13.74)
4h		65	145	C ₂₄ H ₁₃ ClF ₃ N ₅ OS (511.91)	56.15 (56.31)	2.42 (2.56)	13.60 (13.68)	6.14 (6.26)

Table 2. Bioactivity of synthesized azo pyrazoles 4a-h against two plant pathogenic fungi

Compd.	Percent inhibition of growth of fungus at indicated dose											
	<i>Alternaria burnsii</i>						<i>Macrophomina phaseolina</i>					
	100 ppm		500 ppm				100 ppm			500 ppm		
Min.	Max.	Avg.	Min.	Max.	Avg.	Min.	Max.	Avg.	Min.	Max.	Avg.	
4a	58.3	62.7	60.80	97.2	99.1	98.16	50.7	57.2	54.20	89.3	95.2	91.53
4b	60.3	65.2	63.40	100.00	100.00	100.00	53.3	57.4	55.37	94.3	99.2	96.97
4c	58.9	64.1	61.40	98.4	100.00	99.47	49.9	54.1	51.57	90.2	97.3	97.00
4d	56.7	65.8	61.30	97.3	100.00	98.23	48.4	59.2	52.27	90.4	98.0	93.53
4e	51.7	60.1	54.70	84.1	95.8	90.66	31.3	45.7	39.80	80.1	82.3	81.03
4f	54.5	62.3	58.67	89.1	96.7	92.37	40.7	46.8	44.33	81.3	85.3	83.90
4g	52.7	55.3	53.80	82.1	92.5	88.76	34.8	50.1	42.87	79.9	83.4	81.87
4h	49.7	57.3	53.40	87.4	90.3	88.63	37.3	44.3	41.07	78.3	85.3	81.30

in the case of *Macrophomina phaseolina*. The remaining four compounds with one chlorine and three fluorine atoms in the compounds **4e**, **4f**, **4g** and **4h** followed the suit but showed slightly less antifungal activity, 88.63 to 92.37 percent inhibition with *Alternaria burnsii* and 81.03 to 83.90 percent inhibition with *Macrophomina phaseolina* at 500 ppm dose.

On the basis of higher level of percent inhibition values it can be deduced that probably, presence of fluorine enhances the antifungal property of the azopyrazoles. Addition of nitro group appear to enhance the antifungal property.

Experimental

Purity of all the compounds were checked on silica gel G plate using iodine as the detecting agent. Melting points were determined in open capillaries and were uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu 8400 S FT-IR spectrometer in KBr pellets. ^1H NMR (chemical shifts in δ ppm) were recorded using Jeol DRX-300 spectrometer (300 MHz) apparatus with TMS as the internal standard. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol SX 102/Da-600 mass spectrometer. In ^{19}F NMR spectra, TFA was taken as an external standard and chemical shifts δ are reported in hundred parts per million.

2-[(6-Fluoro-benzothiazol-2-yl)-hydrazono]-4,4,4-trifluoro-1-phenyl-butan-1,3-dione (3a) :

2-Amino-6-fluorobenzothiazole (0.01 mol) was dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (8 ml) and water (6 ml) and cooled to 0 °C on ice bath. A cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite (0.02 mol) was added. The cold diazonium salt solution was filtered into a cold solution of 1-phenyl-4,4,4-trifluorobutan-1,3-dione (0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (0.05 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) and stirred it for 2 h and resulting solid was filtered, dried and crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 168 °C, yield 65%; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 3310 (>NH-), 1520 (>C=N-), 1645 (>C=O), 3080 (aromatic); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 ppm) : δ 8.4 (1H, s, >NH), 7.4–7.9 (m, Ar-H); ^{19}F NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$ ppm) : δ -5 to -10 (-CF₃), 30–40 (>C-F); MS (m/z) : 395 (M^+) (Found : C, 51.51; H, 2.11; N, 10.54; S, 8.02. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_9\text{F}_4\text{N}_3\text{O}_2\text{S}$ requires : C, 51.65; H, 2.29; N, 10.63; S, 8.11%).

(1,5-Diphenyl-3-trifluoromethyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-(6-fluoro-benzothiazol-2-yl)-diazene (4a) :

2-[6-Fluoro-benzothiazol-2-yl]-hydrazono]-4,4,4-trifluoro-1-phenyl-butan-1,3-dione (**3a**) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) and a solution of phenyl hydrazine (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 4–5 h on a water bath. Resulting solid was dried and crystallized from ethanol. **4a** : m.p. 145–148 °C, yield 68%; IR (KBr cm^{-1}) : 1560 (-N=N-), 3090 (aromatic), 1660–1720 (>C=C and C=N), 1125 (>C-F); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 ppm) : δ 7.2–8.1 (m, aromatic-H); ^{19}F NMR ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$ ppm) : δ 30–40 (>C-F), -5 to -10 (-CF₃); MS (m/z) : 467 (M^+) (Found : C, 58.84; H, 2.72; N, 14.82; S, 6.74. $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{13}\text{F}_4\text{N}_5\text{S}$ requires : C, 59.10; H, 2.80; N, 14.98; S, 6.86%).

Compounds **4b-h** were prepared similarly. Their physical and analytical data are recorded in Table I.

References

- V. S. Jolly, A. K. Srivastava, S. P. Singh and K. S. Tiwari, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 539.
- O. Sullivan and M. L. Conalty, *Proc. R. Ir. Acad.*, 1980, **80**, 385.
- V. Dhingra, R. Bhatwadekar, L. Agarwal and V. S. Jolly, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **68**, 672.
- M. J. Gorezynski, R. M. Leal, S. L. Mooberry, J. H. Bushweller and M. L. Brown, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **12**, 1029.
- M. Ohkubo, A. Kuno, I. Nakanishi and H. Takasugi, *Chem. Pharm. Bull.*, 1995, **43**, 1497.
- B. S. Jayashree, D. Anuradha and N. K. Venugopala, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2005, **17**, 2093.
- J. Rudolph, H. Thesis, R. Hanke, R. Endermann, L. Johannsd and F. U. Geschke, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2001, **44**, 619.
- P. B. Khedekar, R. H. Bahekar, R. S. Chopade, S. N. Umathe, A. R. Rao and K. P. Bhusari, *Arzneimittelforschung/ Drugs Res.*, 2003, **53**, 640.
- J. J. Wade, C. B. Toso, C. J. Matson and V. L. Stelzer, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1983, **26**, 608.
- K. P. Bhusari, P. B. Khedekar, S. N. Umathe, R. H. Bahekar and A. R. Rao, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2000, **9**, 213.
- E. Kashiyama, L. Hutchinson, M. Chua, S. F. Stinson, L. R. Phillips, G. Kaur, E. A. Sau Sville, T. D. Bradshaw, A. D. Westwell and M. F. G. Stevens, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1999, **42**, 4172.
- B. I. Hutchinson, S. A. Jennings, B. R. Vishnuvajala, A. W. Westwell and M. F. G. Stevens, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2002, **45**, 744.

Note

13. K. Mistry and K. R. Desai, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2006, **45**, 1762.
14. C. J. Monasterious, M. J. Dominguez and N. D. Castro, *Heterocyclic Communications*, 2002, **8**, 275.
15. B. M. Gurupadayya, Y. N. Manohara and M. Gopal, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2005, **15**, 113.
16. V. Sareen, U. Gupta, V. Khatri and S. Chugh, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2009, **18**, 239.
17. V. Sareen, U. Gupta, V. Khatri and S. Chug, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2008, **17**, 355.
18. V. Sareen, V. Khatri, U. Garg, P. Jain and K. Sharma, *Phosphorous, Sulphur and Silicon*, 2007, **182**, 2943.
19. V. Sareen, V. Khatri, P. Jain and K. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2006, **45**, 1288.
20. V. Sareen, V. Khatri, P. Jain and K. Sharma, *Phosphorous, Sulphur and Silicon*, 2010, **185**, 146.
21. V. Sareen, V. Khatri, K. Sharma, D. Shinde and S. Sareen, *Heterocyclic Communications*, 2010 (in press).

